

Singular or plural Oldowan tool-makers during
the Lower Pleistocene in eastern Africa?

Sandrine PRAT

LUCY'S HEIRS – TRIBUTE TO YVES COPPENS

Edited by Jean-Jacques HUBLIN, Aurélien MOUNIER & Nicolas TEYSSANDIER

art. 24 (27) — Published on 5 December 2025
www.cr-palevol.fr

PUBLICATIONS
SCIENTIFIQUES

DIRECTEURS DE LA PUBLICATION / PUBLICATION DIRECTORS :
Gilles Bloch, Président du Muséum national d'Histoire naturelle
Étienne Ghys, Secrétaire perpétuel de l'Académie des sciences

RÉDACTEURS EN CHEF / EDITORS-IN-CHIEF: Michel Laurin (CNRS), Philippe Taquet (Académie des sciences)

ASSISTANTE DE RÉDACTION / ASSISTANT EDITOR: Adenise Lopes (Académie des sciences; cr-palevol@academie-sciences.fr)

MISE EN PAGE / PAGE LAYOUT: Audrina Neveu (Muséum national d'Histoire naturelle; audrina.neveu@mnhn.fr)

RÉVISIONS LINGUISTIQUES DES TEXTES ANGLAIS / ENGLISH LANGUAGE REVISIONS: Kevin Padian (University of California at Berkeley)

RÉDACTEURS ASSOCIÉS / ASSOCIATE EDITORS (*, *took charge of the editorial process of the article/a pris en charge le suivi éditorial de l'article*):

Micropaléontologie/*Micropalaeontology*

Lorenzo Consorti (Institute of Marine Sciences, Italian National Research Council, Trieste)

Paléobotanique/*Palaeobotany*

Cyrille Prestianni (Royal Belgian Institute of Natural Sciences, Brussels)

Anaïs Boura (Sorbonne Université, Paris)

Métazoaires/*Metazoa*

Annalisa Ferretti (Università di Modena e Reggio Emilia, Modena)

Paléoichthyologie/*Palaeoichthyology*

Philippe Janvier (Muséum national d'Histoire naturelle, Académie des sciences, Paris)

Amniotes du Mésozoïque/*Mesozoic amniotes*

Hans-Dieter Sues (Smithsonian National Museum of Natural History, Washington)

Tortues/*Turtles*

Walter Joyce (Universität Freiburg, Switzerland)

Lépidosauromorphes/*Lepidosauromorphs*

Hussam Zaher (Universidade de São Paulo)

Oiseaux/*Birds*

Jingmai O'Connor (Field Museum, Chicago)

Paléomammalogie (mammifères de moyenne et grande taille)/*Palaeomammalogy (large and mid-sized mammals)*

Grégoire Métais (CNRS, Muséum national d'Histoire naturelle, Sorbonne Université, Paris)

Paléomammalogie (petits mammifères sauf Euarchontoglires)/*Palaeomammalogy (small mammals except for Euarchontoglires)*

Robert Asher (Cambridge University, Cambridge)

Paléomammalogie (Euarchontoglires)/*Palaeomammalogy (Euarchontoglires)*

K. Christopher Beard (University of Kansas, Lawrence)

Paléoanthropologie/*Palaeoanthropology*

Aurélien Mounier (CNRS/Muséum national d'Histoire naturelle, Paris)

Archéologie préhistorique (Paléolithique et Mésolithique)/*Prehistoric archaeology (Palaeolithic and Mesolithic)*

Nicolas Teyssandier* (CNRS/Université de Toulouse, Toulouse)

Archéologie préhistorique (Néolithique et âge du bronze)/*Prehistoric archaeology (Neolithic and Bronze Age)*

Marc Vander Linden (Bournemouth University, Bournemouth)

RÉFÉRÉS / REVIEWERS: <https://sciencepress.mnhn.fr/fr/periodiques/comptes-rendus-palevol/referes-du-journal>

COUVERTURE / COVER:

Silhouettes of *Homo habilis* and *Paranthropus boisei* by T. Michael Keesey (<https://www.phylopic.org/>), lanscape of Turkana and stone artefact. Credits: S. Prat/MPK-WTAP.

Comptes Rendus Palevol est indexé dans / *Comptes Rendus Palevol is indexed by:*

- Cambridge Scientific Abstracts
- Current Contents® Physical
- Chemical, and Earth Sciences®
- ISI Alerting Services®
- Geoabstracts, Geobase, Georef, Inspec, Pascal
- Science Citation Index®, Science Citation Index Expanded®
- Scopus®.

Les articles ainsi que les nouveautés nomenclaturales publiés dans *Comptes Rendus Palevol* sont référencés par /
Articles and nomenclatural novelties published in Comptes Rendus Palevol are registered on:

- ZooBank® (<http://zoobank.org>)

Comptes Rendus Palevol est une revue en flux continu publiée par les Publications scientifiques du Muséum, Paris et l'Académie des sciences, Paris
Comptes Rendus Palevol is a fast track journal published by the Museum Science Press, Paris and the Académie des sciences, Paris

Les Publications scientifiques du Muséum publient aussi / *The Museum Science Press also publish:*

Adansonia, Geodiversitas, Zoosystema, Anthropolozologica, European Journal of Taxonomy, Naturae, Cryptogamie sous-sections *Algologie, Bryologie, Mycologie*.

L'Académie des sciences publie aussi / *The Académie des sciences also publishes:*

Comptes Rendus Mathématique, Comptes Rendus Physique, Comptes Rendus Mécanique, Comptes Rendus Chimie, Comptes Rendus Géoscience, Comptes Rendus Biologies.

Diffusion – Publications scientifiques Muséum national d'Histoire naturelle

CP 41 – 57 rue Cuvier F-75231 Paris cedex 05 (France)

Tél. : 33 (0)1 40 79 48 05 / Fax : 33 (0)1 40 79 38 40

diff.pub@mnhn.fr / <https://sciencepress.mnhn.fr>

Académie des sciences, Institut de France, 23 quai de Conti, 75006 Paris.

© This article is licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>)
ISSN (imprimé / *print*): 1631-0683/ ISSN (électronique / *electronic*): 1777-571X

Singular or plural Oldowan tool-makers during the Lower Pleistocene in eastern Africa?

Sandrine PRAT

HNHP/CNRS/MNHN/UPVD, Musée de l'Homme,
17 Place du Trocadéro, F-75016 Paris (France)
sandrine.prat@mnhn.fr

Submitted on 15 February 2024 | Accepted on 3 July 2025 | Published on 5 December 2025

urn:lsid:zoobank.org:pub:AC3F6968-1912-4C55-BF76-5D980241A4ED

Prat S. 2025. — Singular or plural Oldowan tool-makers during the Lower Pleistocene in eastern Africa? *in* Hublin J.-J., Mounier A. & Teyssandier N. (eds), Lucy's Heirs – Tribute to Yves Coppens. *Comptes Rendus Palevol* 24 (27): 545-561. <https://doi.org/10.5852/cr-palevol2025v24a27>

ABSTRACT

Over the last twenty-five years, the study of hominin evolution and archaeological assemblages has become increasingly complex, due to new archaeological and paleoanthropological discoveries, and the advent of innovative analytical approaches. Findings from paleontological and archaeological sites and localities along the East African Rift Valley reveal substantial cultural and biological diversity during the Lower Pleistocene. From this context emerge critical questions about the relationships between the different material cultures and hominins. To explore these questions, I propose a cross-disciplinary approach that examines both the skeletal anatomy of hominins and the associations between hominins and archaeological assemblages in Lower Pleistocene sites and localities in East Africa. Anatomical evidence suggests that the dexterity required to produce Oldowan assemblages was likely not exclusive to the genus *Homo*. Moreover, multiple hominin species appear to have been involved in tool-making, particularly within Oldowan assemblages. These assemblages have been associated with *Homo* sp. and *Homo habilis* (n = 10), *Homo erectus/ergaster* (n = 6), and with a significant number, of *Paranthropus* remains (n = 8). Given this evidence, *Paranthropus* should now be recognized as a stone tool-maker alongside early *Homo*.

KEY WORDS
Material culture,
hominins,
Africa,
Lower Pleistocene,
Oldowan,
Acheulean.

RÉSUMÉ

Singularité ou pluralité des artisans de l'Oldowayen au Pléistocène inférieur en Afrique de l'Est?

Au cours des vingt-cinq dernières années, de nouvelles découvertes archéologiques et paléoanthropologiques, ainsi que des approches analytiques innovantes, ont considérablement enrichi notre compréhension de l'évolution des hominines et des assemblages archéologiques. Les découvertes de sites et de localités paléontologiques et archéologiques le long de la vallée du Rift Est Africain révèlent une diversité culturelle et biologique substantielle durant le Pléistocène inférieur. Cela soulève des questions fondamentales sur les relations entre les hominines et les différentes cultures matérielles. Pour explorer ces questions, je propose une approche interdisciplinaire qui examine à la fois l'anatomie de la main des hominines et les associations entre hominines et assemblages archéologiques dans les sites et localités du Pléistocène inférieur en Afrique de l'Est. Les preuves anatomiques suggèrent que la dextérité requise pour produire des assemblages oldowayens n'est probablement pas exclusive au genre *Homo*. En outre, plusieurs espèces d'hominines semblent avoir été les artisans d'artefacts lithiques, en particulier pour les assemblages oldowayens. Ceux-ci sont associés à *Homo* sp. et *Homo habilis* (n = 10), *Homo erectus/ergaster* (n = 6) et, à un nombre significatif de restes de *Paranthropus* (n = 8). Compte tenu de ces éléments, *Paranthropus* devrait donc être reconnu comme un artisan d'artefacts lithiques au même titre que les premiers représentants du genre *Homo*.

MOTS CLÉS
Culture matérielle,
hominines,
Afrique,
Pleistocène inférieur,
Oldowayen,
Acheuléen.

INTRODUCTION

Hominin evolutionary history depicts a bushy rather than a linear evolutionary history with multiple contemporaneous species or genera in Africa during the Pliocene and Pleistocene and sympatric relationship, for example between *Homo erectus* and *Paranthropus boisei*, as illustrated by footprint evidence (Hatala *et al.* 2024). This indicates significant morphological diversity (Fig. 1) with a reticulated biological evolution and ghost lineages, especially for the genus *Homo* (e.g. Foley 2002; Wood & Loneragan 2008; Wood & Boyle 2016; Lorente-Galdos *et al.* 2019; Caparros & Prat 2021). Likewise, the archaeological record reveals a diversity of assemblages and a non-linear pattern of cultural evolution, exemplified by some Acheulean sites actually older than Oldowan sites (e.g. Kokiselei 4 [Lepre *et al.* 2011]; Konso-Gardula [Asfaw *et al.* 1992; Beyene *et al.* 2023]).

Moreover, the oldest *Homo* fossils from Ledi Geraru in Ethiopia (Villmoare *et al.* 2015, 2025) as well as the specimens older than 2.3 Ma for example from the lower Omo Valley (e.g. Hlusko *et al.* 2024) and from the eastern and western parts of Lake Turkana (e.g. KNM-ER 5431 (Suwa *et al.* 1996; Villmoare *et al.* 2015) and KNM-WT 42718 (Prat *et al.* 2005)) postdate stone tools discovered at the LOM3 archeological site in Kenya by about 500 000 years-1 million years (Ma) (3.3 Ma, Harmand *et al.* 2015, but see also for discussion Domínguez-Rodrigo & Alcalá 2016, 2019; Harmand *et al.* 2019; Archer *et al.* 2020; Key & Proffitt 2024) and cut-marked bones dated to 3.4 Ma from Dikika locality in Ethiopia (McPherron *et al.* 2010, but see also for discussion Domínguez-Rodrigo *et al.* 2011; Thompson *et al.* 2015; Domínguez-Rodrigo & Alcalá 2016). The Dikika area is also known for the discovery of a juvenile skeleton of *A. afarensis* (Alemseged *et al.* 2006). The Lomekwi archaeological site LOM3 (3.3 Ma) is in the same chronological range as the species *Australopithecus afarensis* (3.8-3.0 Ma) and was discovered in the Lomekwi area, where hominin remains attributed to *Kenyanthropus platyops* were also found (Leakey *et al.* 2001). However, due to the high level of distortion of KNM-WT 40000 (*K. platyops* holotype which is the only cranium of this species), it is difficult to establish whether it is a valid taxon or a variant of *A. afarensis* (White 2003), a species considered by some authors to be the ancestor of the genera *Homo* and *Paranthropus* (see Kimbel & Deleuzene 2009 for a review).

Therefore, these findings from Lomekwi and Dikika challenge the exclusive association of lithic artefacts (stone-tool use and stone-tool making) with the genus *Homo*. They question specific attribution of lithic artefact manufacture to the genus *Homo* and the validity of this criterion for defining our genus. Indeed, the diagnosis of the genus *Homo* and the criteria for this classification are still hotly debated, and take into account anatomical, morphological, behavioural, and philosophical considerations (see for a review Prat 2022). Among the criteria proposed by Leakey and colleagues (Leakey *et al.* 1964) power and precision grip manual abilities were central. However, tool-making was mentioned in the section entitled “Cultural Association”

but not in the *Homo habilis* diagnosis. Consequently, the role of archaeological remains in defining the genus *Homo* highlights the potential relationships in East Africa between Oldowan, Acheulean and Lower Pleistocene hominins.

The discoveries made in the lower Omo Valley, in the extreme south-west of Ethiopia, are of particular interest in this context. Research in this region initially began with work by Camille Arambourg in the early 1930s, following surveys carried out by Dr Brumpt as part of the explorations led by Viscount Robert du Bour de Bozas in 1902. New expeditions were carried out from 1966 onwards, as part of the International Omo Research Expedition (IORE) initiated by Francis Clark Howell, Louis Leakey, Camille Arambourg and Yves Coppens (who led the French side of the expedition with Camille Arambourg, and then alone from 1970 to 1976, and to whom this issue is dedicated). The aim of this international, multidisciplinary expedition was to prospect and excavate the rich fossil deposits of the lower Omo Valley. Research in this region was resumed in 2006 as part of the OGRE (Omo Group Research Expedition) led by Jean-Renaud Boisserie (e.g. Boisserie *et al.* 2008). This region, with a sedimentary sequence almost 800 metres thick, is of considerable importance for the study of hominins, palaeoenvironmental reconstructions and relationships between hominin evolution, environment and material culture. The lower Omo Valley comprises several Oldowan sites (e.g. Chavaillon 1970; Delagnes *et al.* 2011; Delagnes *et al.* 2023) and a very large number of hominin remains (e.g. Coppens 1977; Hlusko *et al.* 2024). In addition, the Usno and Shungura formations are among one the longest sedimentary sequences bear hominin remains and also provide data for tracing climatic changes between 3 and 1 Ma (e.g. Coppens 1978; Alemseged *et al.* 2007; Boisserie *et al.* 2008; Bibi *et al.* 2013; Bedane *et al.* 2025).

This overview is an updated of a paper published in 2023 (Prat 2023). It focuses on the morphological attributes underlying hominin remains manual skills, and the associations between eastern african hominin remains (more than 950 in the study corpus) and Oldowan assemblages as evidenced in palaeontological and archaeological records from 3.0 to 1.2 Ma, with an update of some datations. A site description is included where hominin remains were discovered in an archaeological site, with a particular focus on the sites where Pr. Yves Coppens worked.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

The discussion on hominin remains (anatomical parts, taxonomy), archaeological sites, spatial context, and other relevant data (i.e., as primary data, without entering into discussions) is based on data from the literature, used here at face value. However, finding detailed contextual information on hominin remains, and depositional processes, whether *in situ* or on the surface, and their proximity to archaeological artefacts can be challenging. Despite thorough research, it would appear that certain specific associations may be largely overlooked. Regarding the taxonomy of hominin remains, some

FIG. 1. — Chronological framework of hominin taxa (above) and material cultures (below).

specimens are referred to *Homo ergaster* or *Homo erectus* by different authors, according to diverse nomenclatures (Reed *et al.* 2023). To avoid confusion, in this context, I refer to them as *Homo ergaster/erectus*.

According to Key and Proffitt, the earliest Oldowan assemblages may date from 3.020 or 3.181 Ma and, according to an optimal linear estimation (OLE), they fall within the range of 2.622–3.436 Ma (Key & Proffitt 2024). In archaeological terminology, the terms Oldowan and Acheulean are used without distinguishing the early Oldowan and Developed Oldowan, despite differences between early (*c.* 2.6–2.3 Ma) and later Oldowan sites (*c.* 2.0–1.7 Ma) (e.g. Harmand 2009; Roche *et al.* 2009; de la Torre 2011; Goldman-Neuman & Hovers 2012; Potts 2012; Delagnes

et al. 2023). The Oldowan can be considered as multiple specialized adaptations (Clark & Linares-Matás 2024). Furthermore, in many publications, particularly the earliest ones, the only terminology used is Oldowan or Acheulean (e.g. Leakey 1971; Chavaillon 1976; Harris & Herbich 1978; Kimbel *et al.* 1996; Plummer *et al.* 2023).

Determining whether a hominin found at an archaeological site or on the surface was the stone tool-makers is always challenging. The place of death may not correspond to the living area, and sites can sometimes be palimpsests and/or have undergone complex geological and sedimentation processes over time. However, applying Occam's razor, the most parsimonious hypothesis is that the hominins present at a site are the ones responsible for the material culture found there.

Specifically, it is more reasonable to assume that stone tool-makers correspond to the species identified in the site's sedimentary layers rather than to species absent from them. This is generally the case when specimens of the genus *Homo* are found, but is less systematic for other genera. Moreover, this continues to be one of the most widely accepted hypotheses, especially for Middle and Upper Paleolithic sites.

The reliability of the association between hominins and archaeological sites is categorized following the framework used by Grine *et al.* (2022) for species attribution of post-cranial remains. Two categories are proposed: 1) High Confidence 1 (HC1), where hominin remains were found in archaeological site (in archaeological layers and on the surface of the excavation due to erosion processes); and 2) High Confidence 2 (HC2), categorizing hominin remains found less than 400 metres from the archaeological site, within the same chrono-stratigraphic layer.

RESULTS

OVERVIEW OF ANATOMICAL CONSTRAINTS

Concerning the anatomical prerequisites, the morphological evidence indicates that enhanced dexterity and anatomical capabilities were required for using or making stone tools. This infers in particular “pad-to-pad” precision grasping, as defined by Napier (1956) and Almécija & Alba (2014), involving the “perfect” opposition of the thumb and finger's proximal pulp areas, which can be facilitated by a longer thumb relative to the remaining fingers. This also includes forceful precision gripping and precision handling as described by Marzke (1997), deduced from the carpometacarpal joint of the thumb and the metacarpophalangeal joint of the thumb and the fingers involved. Such morphological evidence and muscular insertions are observed on two additional hominin genera to *Homo* (for a review see also Kivell 2015): *Australopithecus* (specifically *A. afarensis* [e.g. Marzke 1983, 1997, 2013; Tocheri *et al.* 2003; Kivell *et al.* 2011, 2020; Almécija & Alba 2014; Kunze *et al.* 2024], *A. africanus* [e.g. Green & Gordon 2008; Skinner *et al.* 2015; Richmond *et al.* 2016], *A. sediba* [e.g. Kivell *et al.* 2011; Bardo *et al.* 2018; Dunmore *et al.* 2020]) and *Paranthropus* (*P. robustus* and *P. boisei* see below), and therefore extends beyond the genus *Homo*. Experimental biomechanics and musculoskeletal modelling also offer valuable insights into the functional anatomy of the upper limb, particularly in stone tool production (Tocheri *et al.* 2003; Rolian *et al.* 2011; Williams *et al.* 2012; Williams-Hatala *et al.* 2018; Key *et al.* 2019; Macchi *et al.* 2021; Manafzadeh & Gatesy 2021; Williams-Hatala *et al.* 2021; Kivell *et al.* 2022) and can complement anatomical and archaeological field data.

Concerning the Pleistocene fossil record after 2 Ma, the anatomy of hand remains from Olduvai Gorge (misspelling of the Maa word Oldupai, Tanzania, i.e., OH 7 (1.84 Ma) and OH 86 (1.86 Ma), and from Ileret (Kenya, i.e., KNM-ER 47000, 1.5 Ma) was conducive to stone tool use and stone tool-making. In particular, the OH 7 late juvenile

hand (1.84 Ma) from Oldupai Gorge shows a fully opposable thumb and capabilities for power and precision gripping (Leakey *et al.* 1964). Leakey, Tobias and Napier in 1964, pointed out the tool-making abilities of this specimen, whereas Napier (1962) was more cautious, highlighting that “There is less certainty about toolmaking which involves not only a peripheral but also a central intellectual factor as Oakley has long insisted” (Napier 1962: 411)”. The mixed attributes of OH 7 (precision grip abilities and climbing adaptation) were emphasized by Susman & Creel (1979). Furthermore, although OH 7 has been allocated to *Homo habilis* (Leakey *et al.* 1964), some authors consider that the phalangeal morphologies are closer to those of *Paranthropus* (Moyà-Solà *et al.* 2008). Moreover, the manual proximal phalanx (OH 86, 1.84 Ma) allocated to the genus *Homo*, is considered to represent the earliest modern human-like hand anatomy, showing reduced postural and locomotor pressures and a decrease in arboreal adaptations (Domínguez-Rodrigo *et al.* 2015). OH 86 is distinct in size and shape from both *Australopithecus/Paranthropus* and the OH 7 hand bones. Its taxonomic classification is challenging, but it is generally considered as *Homo*, different from OH 7 (*H. habilis* holotype) and attributed rather to *H. erectus* type (Diez-Martín *et al.* 2015). Moreover, the third metacarpal styloid process found in Kaitio, West Turkana, Kenya (with a morphology typical of the modern humans/Neanderthal hand but absent in Pliocene and Lower Pleistocene hominins) suggests that this distinctive complex of radial carpometacarpal joints emerged at early as 1.42 Ma for the genus *Homo* (Ward *et al.* 2014).

Concerning *Paranthropus*, the hand anatomy of *P. boisei*, illustrated by the KNM-ER 47000 specimen (Ileret, East Turkana, Kenya), dated to 1.5 Ma, indicates that the fine precision gripping capacity and manual dexterity of this species is compatible with stone tool use or stone tool-making as also seen in earlier australopithecine species such as *A. africanus* (e.g. Kivell *et al.* 2011; Richmond *et al.* 2016), but not a robust thumb as observed in *H. erectus/H. ergaster*. This reflects adaptations to the intensification of precision gripping and tool use (Richmond *et al.* 2020). *Paranthropus* individuals present increased wrist mobility, which could improve the accuracy of force production during stone tool-making and stone tool use (e.g. Williams *et al.* 2010; Williams *et al.* 2014), or even during throwing, as shown in *H. erectus* (Roach *et al.* 2013; Roach & Lieberman 2014). However, Moyà-Solà *et al.* (2008) proposed that the *Paranthropus* hand structure which lacks the enlarged first metacarpal typical of *Homo*, might also reflect adaptations for feeding activities as seen in extant hominids (e.g. Marzke *et al.* 2015; Neufuss *et al.* 2018; Gérard *et al.* 2022). The anatomy of *Paranthropus*, particularly elements like OH 80 (e.g. radial morphology compatible with grasping abilities, used for power and precision grips) aligns with the abilities required for stone tool production (Domínguez-Rodrigo *et al.* 2013). However, as noted by Grine *et al.* 2022, it is very difficult to associate isolated post-cranial elements more specifically with the genus *Homo* or *Paranthropus*, given that these two genera are stratigraphically associated.

Fig. 2. — Location of *Homo habilis sensu lato* remains in association with Oldowan sites. Credits: background map NASA/Internet Archive.

OVERVIEW OF THE ARCHAEOLOGICAL DATA

In Eastern Africa, between 3 and 1.2 Ma, 25 documented instances (which correspond to 20 archaeological sites) of a high-confidence association between lithic and palaeoanthropological remains have been reported (Table 1).

Association between Oldowan assemblages and Homo habilis sensu lato

The association between the Oldowan and early *Homo* specimens can be observed in six occurrences (in Ethiopia, at Hadar, A.L. 666 (HC1), and Fejej, Fj-1a (HC2); in Kenya, in the western part of Lake Turkana, Lokalalei site complex (HC2); in Tanzania, in Oldupai Gorge, MNK Skull site (HC1), DK site (HC2) and Ewass Oldupa site (HC2) dated between 2.3 and 1.67 Ma (Table 1; Fig. 2). I describe here the two archaeological sites where hominin remains were discovered in archaeological layers or at the surface of the excavation (HC1).

The first is the archaeological site named A.L. 666, in the Hadar region in Ethiopia. The lithic assemblage (34 artefacts including 14 found *in situ*) is typical of the Oldowan (Kimbel *et al.* 1996; Plummer 2004; Goldman-Neuman & Hovers 2012). These assemblages are dated to *c.* 2.35 Ma by the Bouroukie Tuff 3 (Campisano & Feibel 2008) and between

2.3 and 1.9 Ma based on the fauna (Rowan *et al.* 2022). A maxilla (A.L. 666-1) was found on the surface of the hill (at the base). This latter shows clear early *Homo* traits and was assigned to *Homo aff. H. habilis* (Kimbel *et al.* 1996; Kimbel *et al.* 1997). However, Spoor *et al.* (2015) have considered that its morphology is not compatible with OH7, and therefore with *H. habilis*, and furthermore does not present the facial morphology observed in *H. rudolfensis*. For the above-mentioned authors, the morphology of A.L. 666-1 is more derived toward early *H. erectus/ergaster*.

The second high-confidence site (HC1) is MNK Skull site from Middle Bed II at Oldupai (Leakey 1971; de la Torre *et al.* 2021), which yielded an Oldowan assemblage and two *in situ Homo habilis* specimens (OH 13, paratype of *Homo habilis*), as well as dental remains catalogued as OH 15 (Leakey *et al.* 1964; Tobias 1991) dated to *c.* 1.67 Ma (de la Torre *et al.* 2021).

Association between Oldowan assemblages and Paranthropus (P. boisei)

The association between *Paranthropus boisei* specimens and Oldowan assemblages can be observed in four sites (in Kenya at Homa Peninsula, Nyayanga site (HC1); in the western part of Lake Turkana, Kokiselei 1 (HC1) and at Koobi Fora,

TABLE 1. — Association between hominin remains and archaeological assemblage with a High Confidence level (HC). Abbreviations: **HC1**, hominin remains have been found in an archaeological site, which includes both in archaeological layers and remains found on the surface of the excavation due to erosion processes; **HC2**, hominin remains have been found less than 400 meters from the archaeological site, within the same chrono-stratigraphic layer.

Locality	Region	Age (Ma)	Hominins	Industry	Category of reliability
Association between Oldowan assemblages and <i>Homo</i> (<i>H. habilis sensu lato</i> and <i>Homo</i> sp.)					
A.L. 666	Hadar (Ethiopia)	c. 2.35 (Campisano & Feibel 2008) 2.3 and 1.9 (Rowan <i>et al.</i> 2022)	A.L. 666-1 <i>Homo aff. H. habilis</i> (Kimbel <i>et al.</i> 1997)	Oldowan (Kimbel <i>et al.</i> 1996)	HC 1
Lokalalei 1, Gajh5	West Turkana (Kenya)	2.34 +/- 0.04 (Prat <i>et al.</i> 2005)	KNM-WT 42718 Early <i>Homo</i> (Prat <i>et al.</i> 2005)	Oldowan (Prat <i>et al.</i> 2005)	HC 2
FJ-1a	Fejej (Ethiopia)	1.95-1.90 (Chapon <i>et al.</i> 2005)	Fj-1-Hd1, Hd3, Hd4 <i>Homo aff. Homo habilis</i> (de Lumley & Marchal 2004)	Oldowan (e.g. Asfaw <i>et al.</i> 1991; de Lumley & Beyene 2004; Barsky <i>et al.</i> 2011)	HC 2
DK	Oldupai Gorge (Tanzania)	1.87-1.84 (Deino 2012)	OH 24 <i>Homo habilis</i> (Leakey <i>et al.</i> 1971)	Oldowan (Leakey 1971; de la Torre & Mora 2005)	HC 2
Ewass Oldupa	Oldupai Gorge (Tanzania)	c. 1.82 (Blumenschine <i>et al.</i> 2003; Deino 2012; McHenry 2012)	OH 65 <i>Homo habilis</i> (Blumenschine <i>et al.</i> 2012; Clarke 2012)	Oldowan (Mercader <i>et al.</i> 2021)	HC 2
MNK Skull	Oldupai Gorge (Tanzania)	c. 1.67 (de la Torre <i>et al.</i> 2021)	OH 13 Paratype <i>Homo habilis</i> OH 15 <i>Homo habilis</i> (Leakey <i>et al.</i> 1964; Tobias 1991)	Oldowan (Leakey 1971; de la Torre <i>et al.</i> 2021)	HC 1
Association between Oldowan assemblages and <i>Paranthropus</i>					
Nyayanga, excavation 3	Lake Victoria (Kenya)	3.03-2.58 (Plummer <i>et al.</i> 2023)	KNM-NG 77316 <i>Paranthropus</i> (Plummer <i>et al.</i> 2023)	Oldowan (Plummer <i>et al.</i> 2023)	HC 1
Kokiselei 1 FxJh6	West Turkana (Kenya)	1.79 (Boës <i>et al.</i> 2024)	KNM-WT 37744, 37747, 37748, 37100 <i>Paranthropus boisei</i> (Prat <i>et al.</i> 2003)	Oldowan (Roche <i>et al.</i> 2003; Arroyo <i>et al.</i> 2020)	HC 1
FxJj 20	Koobi Fora (Kenya)	1.65 +/- 0.05 (Feibel <i>et al.</i> 1989)	KNM-ER 3230 <i>Paranthropus boisei</i> (Wood 1991)	Oldowan (Harris & Herbich 1978)	HC 1
BK site level 4, Bed II	Olduvai Gorge (Tanzania)	1.34 (Domínguez-Rodrigo <i>et al.</i> 2013)	OH 80 <i>Paranthropus boisei</i> (Domínguez-Rodrigo <i>et al.</i> 2013)	Oldowan (Domínguez-Rodrigo <i>et al.</i> 2009)	HC 1
Association between Oldowan assemblages, <i>Homo</i> and <i>Paranthropus</i>					
OMO 57/5	Lower Omo Valley (Ethiopia)	2.32-2.23 (McDougall & Brown 2008)	OMO 57/5-1972-371 <i>Paranthropus aff. aethiopicus</i> (Coppens 1977; Suwa 1990; Wood & Leakey 2011) OMO 57/5-1972-319 Indet. (White 1988) Non robust indet. hominin (Suwa 1990) <i>Homo aff. Homo</i> sp. (Wood & Leakey 2011)	Oldowan (Coppens <i>et al.</i> 1973; Chavaillon 1976)	HC 1
FLK NN level 3	Oldupai Gorge (Tanzania)	1.84 (Deino 2012)	OH 7 cranial remains <i>Homo habilis</i> (Holotype) (Leakey <i>et al.</i> 1964)	Oldowan (Leakey <i>et al.</i> 1964; Leakey 1971)	HC 1
FLK NN level 3	Oldupai Gorge (Tanzania)	1.84 (Deino 2012)	OH 7 hand bones <i>Homo habilis</i> (Leakey <i>et al.</i> 1964) or <i>Paranthropus</i> (Moyà-Solà <i>et al.</i> 2008)	Oldowan (Leakey <i>et al.</i> 1964; Leakey 1971)	HC 1
FLK NN level 3	Oldupai Gorge (Tanzania)	1.84 (Deino 2012)	OH 8 foot bones <i>Homo habilis</i> (paratype) (Day & Napier 1964; Leakey <i>et al.</i> 1964)	Oldowan (Leakey <i>et al.</i> 1964; Leakey 1971)	HC 1

Table 1. — Continuation.

Locality	Region	Age (Ma)	Hominins	Industry	Category of reliability
FLK level 22	Oldupai Gorge (Tanzania)	1.84 (Deino 2012)	OH 5 Holotype of <i>Paranthropus boisei</i> (Leakey 1959)	Oldowan (Leakey 1971)	HC 1
FLK level 22	Oldupai Gorge (Tanzania)	1.84 (Deino 2012)	OH 6 <i>Homo habilis</i> (Tobias 1991)	Oldowan (Leakey 1971)	HC 1
FLK level 22	Oldupai Gorge (Tanzania)	1.84 (Deino 2012)	OH 35 <i>Paranthropus boisei</i> or <i>Homo habilis</i> (Leakey et al. 1964)	Oldowan (Leakey 1971)	HC 1
FxJj 38	Koobi Fora (Kenya)	1.78-1.52 (Mana et al. 2019)	KNM-ER 1805 <i>Homo</i> sp. but taxonomical allocation under discussion (Leakey 1974; Prat 2002)	Oldowan (Harris & Herbich 1978)	HC 1
FxJj 38	Koobi Fora (Kenya)	1.78-1.52 (Mana et al. 2019)	KNM-ER 1806 <i>Paranthropus boisei</i> (Leakey 1974; Wood 1991)	Oldowan (Harris & Herbich 1978)	HC 1
Association between Oldowan assemblages and <i>Homo erectus</i>/<i>Homo ergaster</i>					
Garba IV, level E	Melka Kunture (Ethiopia)	Slightly older than 1.7 (Morgan et al. 2012; Tamrat et al. 2014; Gallotti & Mussi 2015)	MK 81 GAR IVE 0043 early <i>Homo erectus</i> / <i>Homo ergaster</i> (Condemi 2004)	Oldowan (Gallotti & Mussi 2015; Mussi et al. 2023)	HC 1
PTK site	Oldupai Gorge (Tanzania)	1.84 (Deino 2012)	OH 86 <i>Homo erectus</i> -like (Diez-Martín et al. 2015; Domínguez-Rodrigo et al. 2015)	Oldowan (Domínguez-Rodrigo et al. 2015)	HC 1
Naiyena Engol 1	West Turkana (Kenya)	1.75 +/- 0.05 (Roche et al. 2003)	KNM-WT 37745 <i>Homo</i> sp. (aff. <i>H. ergaster</i>) (Prat et al. 2003)	Oldowan (Roche et al. 2003)	HC 1
FxJh5	Melka Kunture (Ethiopia)	1.6-1.5 (Morgan et al. 2012; Tamrat et al. 2014)	Gombore IB-7594	Oldowan (Chavaillon et al. 1977; Chavaillon & Berthelet 2004)	HC 1
Gombore I			early <i>Homo erectus</i> <i>Homo</i> sp. (Chavaillon et al. 1977; Coppens 2004; Di Vincenzo et al. 2015)		
Association between Oldowan, Acheulean assemblages and early <i>Homo erectus</i>/<i>Homo ergaster</i>					
DAN 5	Afar Region (Ethiopia)	1.6-1.5 (Semaw et al. 2020)	DAN5/P1 early <i>Homo erectus</i> (Semaw et al. 2020; Baab et al. 2022; Bruner et al. 2023)	Oldowan and Acheulean (Semaw et al. 2020)	HC 1
BSN12	Afar Region (Ethiopia)	1.26 +/- 0.03 (Semaw et al. 2020)	BSN12/P1 <i>Homo erectus</i> (Semaw et al. 2020; Baab et al. 2022)	Oldowan and Acheulean (Semaw et al. 2020)	HC 1

FXJj 20 (HC1); in Tanzania, at Oldupai Gorge, BK site (HC1), dated between 3.03-2.58 and 1.34 Ma (Table 1; Fig. 3). Here I describe the oldest and youngest sites with hominin remains discovered in archaeological layers or at the surface of the excavation (HC1).

The oldest site with an association between Oldowan and *Paranthropus* remains is Nyayanga, which in the Homa Peninsula near Lake Victoria's Winam Gulf in Kenya. This site revealed one of the oldest Oldowan assemblages, dated between 3.032 Ma and 2.581 Ma (Plummer et al. 2023), with 135 *in situ* artefacts (excavations 3 and 5) and faunal remains, some of which bear cutmarks. The lithic artefacts show evidence of unifacial, bifacial, and multifacial reduction, and are comparable to lithics from other Oldowan sites. Use wear analyses indicate the processing of plant and animal tissues. From excavation 3, KNM-NG 77316 (a left lower

molar fragment) was found *in situ*, associated with Oldowan artefacts (HC1) and KNM-NG 77315 (a left upper molar) from the surface. Both teeth are assigned to *Paranthropus* based on their morphology and metrics.

The youngest site illustrating an association between *Paranthropus* specimens and Oldowan artefacts is BK site in Oldupai Gorge (Bed II) in Tanzania. In this site dated to 1.34 Ma, a partial *Paranthropus boisei* skeleton (OH 80) was discovered *in situ* in level 4 (HC1) (Domínguez-Rodrigo et al. 2013). This partial skeleton includes four postcranial bones and nine upper teeth, allocated to *P. boisei* on the basis of their morphology, dimensions, and postcranial bone section properties. This find represents the first partial skeleton attributed to *P. boisei*. A large Oldowan assemblage and numerous vertebrate fossils, including some with cut marks, were also unearthed in level 4 (Domínguez-Rodrigo et al. 2009).

FIG. 3. — Location of *Paranthropus* (*P. aethiopicus* and *P. boisei*) remains in association with Oldowan sites. Credits: background map NASA/Internet Archive.

Association between Oldowan assemblages and *Homo* and *Paranthropus*

The association between *Homo habilis* (*Homo habilis*, *Homo* sp.), *Paranthropus* (*P. aff. P. aethiopicus* and *Paranthropus boisei*) specimens and Oldowan assemblages is documented in four sites (in Ethiopia, in the lower Omo Valley, OMO 57-5 (HC1), in Kenya at Koobi Fora, FXJj 38 (HC1), and in Tanzania, at Oldupai Gorge at FLK level 22 and FLK NN level 3 (HC1) dated between 2.32 and 1.78-1.52 Ma (Fig. 4).

I present here two sites from Oldupai gorge, which are of key importance in hominin evolution as they contain the holotypes of the species *Paranthropus boisei* and *Homo habilis* and OMO 57-5, in the lower Omo Valley in Ethiopia, discovered thanks to the work of Jean Chavaillon and Yves Coppens.

At OMO 57-5 (Member F of the Shungura Formation), the 40 square metres excavation revealed four hominin tooth fragments and an *in situ* quartz flake along with 16 surface artefacts (Coppens *et al.* 1973; Chavaillon 1976). One tooth fragment (OMO 57/5-1972-371, a left lower second premolar, HC1) is assigned to *P. aff. P. aethiopicus*, based on its morphology (Coppens *et al.* 1973; Coppens 1977; Suwa 1990; Wood & Leakey 2011). Another dental remain (OMO 57/5-1972-319), a left upper first premolar, is classified as indeterminate (White 1988), or as belonging to a non-robust indeterminate hominin (Suwa 1990), or *Homo aff. Homo* sp. (Wood & Leakey 2011). The Oldowan assemblage is characterized by systematic knapping and therefore not derived from natural fragmentation (de la Torre 2004). The deposit is dated between 2.32 Ma and 2.23 Ma (McDougall & Brown 2008).

In Tanzania, at Oldupai, the FLK level 22 has yielded a dense Oldowan assemblage (over 255 artefacts) and abundant mammal fossils (over 3500) (Leakey 1971) dated between 1.845 +/- 0.002 and 1.839 +/- 0.005 Ma (Blumenschine *et al.* 2003, 2012). Four hominin individuals were identified, including the cranium OH 5 (HC1), the *Paranthropus boisei* holotype (formerly *Zinjanthropus boisei*, Leakey 1959). The site also revealed some teeth and calvaria fragments (OH 6), attributed to *H. habilis* (HC1) and some post-cranial bones (tibia and fibula, OH 35) attributed to either *P. boisei* or *H. habilis* as these fossils are associated with OH 5 or OH 6.

The same association is also observed at FLK NN level 3 in Bed I at Oldupai. In this site numerous Oldowan stone artefacts were found alongside five hominin individuals, catalogued as OH 7 (juvenile mandible and cranial fragments and hand bones), holotype of *Homo habilis* (Leakey *et al.* 1964), OH 8 foot bones (paratype of *H. habilis*, Leakey *et al.* 1964), initially reported by Day & Napier (1964), OH 48 clavicle, OH 43 metatarsals and OH 49 radial shaft. The estimated age of these remains is 1.84 Ma (Deino 2012). OH 7 cranial remains are identified as *H. habilis*, but the allocation of the hand (OH7) and foot bones (OH8) to the same species is based on the parsimonious hypothesis of spatial association (Grine *et al.* 2022). However, some researchers have suggested that these hand bones (OH7) should belong to *Paranthropus* (Moyà-Solà *et al.* 2008). Conversely, the morphology of the OH 8 hallux tarsometatarsal complex is very similar to that of modern humans, which supports an attribute to the genus *Homo* (Berillon 1999).

Fig. 4. — Location of *Homo habilis* and *Paranthropus* remains in association with Oldowan sites. Credits: background map NASA/Internet Archive.

Fig. 5. — Location of *Homo erectus*/*Homo ergaster* in association with Oldowan sites. Credits: background map NASA/Internet Archive.

Association between Oldowan assemblages and *Homo erectus*/*Homo ergaster*

The association between *Homo erectus*/*Homo ergaster* specimens and Oldowan assemblages is documented in four sites (in Ethiopia, at Melka Kunture, Garba IV level 5 (HC1) and Gombore I (HC1); in Kenya in the western part of Lake Turkana, Naiyena Engol 1 (HC1); in Tanzania, at Oldupai, PTK site (HC1)) dated between 2 and 1.5–1.6 Ma (Fig. 5). I present here the discoveries from Melka Kunture, where Professor Yves Coppens worked and published some remains.

In Melka Kunture, the site Garba IV, level D, yielded an Oldowan lithic assemblage and a young child's mandible (MK 81 GAR IVE 0043, HC 1) attributed to early *Homo erectus*/*Homo ergaster* (Condemi 2004; Gallotti & Mussi 2015; Zanolli *et al.* 2016; Mussi *et al.* 2023). These remains were estimated to be slightly older than 1.7 Ma (Morgan *et al.* 2012; Tamrat *et al.* 2014; Gallotti & Mussi 2015), but are more recently considered to be around 2 Ma (Mussi *et al.* 2023). This site also reveals that hominins adapted to the high-altitude environment of the highlands of Melka Kunture (at or above 2000 m a.s.l.) during the Lower Pleistocene.

During the excavation of the Melka Kunture Gombore I site, a well-preserved distal portion of a left humerus (Gombore IB-7594, formally Melka Kunture 3 or MK3, HC1) was found *in situ* (Chavaillon & Berthelet 2004), alongside rich faunal and Oldowan assemblages, predominantly made up of pebble tools. The humerus is dated to 1.5–1.6 Ma (Morgan *et al.* 2012; Tamrat *et al.* 2014). Most authors attribute this specimen to the genus *Homo* (Senut 1979) and more specifically to *Homo* sp. (Chavaillon *et al.* 1977; Di Vincenzo *et al.* 2015) or to *Homo erectus* or aff. *erectus* (Coppens 2004; Cazenave *et al.* 2017). According to Coppens (2004), the robust humerus should be allocated to *Homo habilis*. However, Lague & Jungers (1996) suggest that this specimen should be assigned to *Paranthropus boisei*.

Association between Oldowan, Acheulean assemblages and early *Homo erectus*/*Homo ergaster*

The association between *Homo erectus*/*Homo ergaster* specimens and Oldowan and Acheulean artefacts can be observed in two sites in Ethiopia, Dana Aoule North (DAN 5) and Busidima North (BSN 12), in the Afar region (HC1) dated between 1.6 and 1.26 Ma respectively.

In Ethiopia, DAN5 and BSN 12 sites at Gona in the Afar region have yielded significant hominin fossils in association with both Oldowan and Acheulean assemblages, as well as cut-marked bones (Semaw *et al.* 2020). The age of the DAN 5 hominin and lithic assemblage is estimated between 1.6 and 1.5 Ma. The well-preserved hominin skull (occipital and left maxilla), catalogued as DAN5/P1 (HC1) was found *in situ*, with one Oldowan core and six manuports. Other cranial parts, along with freshly exposed Mode 1 and Mode 2 artefacts, were found on the surface of the DAN5 hominin locality. Similar collections were also found in the same stratigraphic area, approximately 140 metres towards the south-southwest (DAN5-South) and about 50 metres towards the west-northwest (DAN5-West). Based on morphology,

shape and size analysis, this skull is assigned to *Homo erectus* (Semaw *et al.* 2020; Baab *et al.* 2022; Bruner *et al.* 2023), and presents some similarities with the *Homo erectus* crania found at Dmanisi (1.77 Ma in Georgia), KNM-ER 42700 (1.6–1.5 Ma in Kenya) and KNM-OL 45500 (0.95 Ma in Kenya), and significant differences with Asian *Homo erectus*. At site BSN12, nearly six kilometers southwest of DAN5, another hominin fossil (right orbital margin and frontal squama) catalogued as BSN12/P1 (HC1), was found closely associated with both Oldowan and Acheulean assemblages (Semaw *et al.* 2020) dated to 1.262 ± 0.034 Ma. In terms of its anatomy and size, this robust hominin shares characteristics with *Homo erectus* from Indonesia and Eastern Asia, as well as others from the Middle Awash, Ethiopia (OH 9 and BOU-VP-2/66) and Buia, Eritrea (UA-31) (Semaw *et al.* 2020; Baab *et al.* 2022). According to Semaw *et al.* (2020) Acheulean toolmakers produced picks and handaxes alongside Mode 1 stone tools (i.e., Oldowan), whenever they needed sharp cutting flakes.

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

The relationships between hominins and Lower Pleistocene material cultures has long been a subject of debate in evolutionary anthropology. However, it is important to note that the scarcity of associations between palaeoanthropological remains and archaeological artefacts can bias our understanding of hominin evolution (Barr & Wood 2024). The exclusive attribution of Oldowan assemblages to *Homo* species is challenged by the temporal and geographical overlap with other taxa such as *P. boisei*, *P. aethiopicus*, *P. robustus* and *A. garhi*. While the ability to manufacture Oldowan artefacts has often been attributed solely to the genus *Homo*, there is growing evidence to suggest that this skill may have been mastered by other hominins, including *Paranthropus*. Indeed, for example Brain *et al.* (1988), Susman (1991), Wood (1997) and more recently Key & Proffitt (2024), highlighted the possibility of a more diverse range of toolmakers. However, Wood & Constantino (2007) noted that is no firm evidence either supporting or refuting *P. boisei*'s ability to manufacture and use stone tools.

Our research clearly illustrates that Oldowan artefacts are not solely associated with *Homo* species (*H. habilis*, and *Homo* sp., ten occurrences) and *H. erectus/ergaster* (six occurrences) but also with *Paranthropus* (at least eight occurrences). The close association of *Paranthropus* remains with Oldowan assemblages, along with anatomical evidence suggesting their potential role in tool-making, indicates that they were involved, alongside early *Homo*, in stone tool production and stone tool use. This observation challenges the traditional notion that stone tool-making is exclusive to and a defining characteristic of the genus *Homo*. Restricting the attribution of tool-making abilities to the genus *Homo*, can no longer be considered valid for the Lower Pleistocene in East Africa. The association between Oldowan assemblages and *Paranthropus boisei* remains, although convincing, has

been a source of debate and hesitation among researchers, particularly when it comes to considering the possibility that *P. boisei* was a stone tool-maker. This hesitation is evident in fluctuating interpretations of fossil finds at various sites. At Oldupai Gorge, the discovery of the FLK level 22 site, which included the famous cranium OH 5 (the holotype of *P. boisei*, originally named *Zinjanthropus boisei* by Leakey in 1959 (Leakey 1959)), initially led to the suggestion that *P. boisei* was a stone tool-maker. However, subsequent discoveries of *Homo habilis* remains led to a revised interpretation by Louis Leakey and co-authors “while it is possible that *Zinjanthropus* and *Homo habilis* both made stone tools, it is probable that the latter was the more advanced tool maker and that the *Zinjanthropus* skull represents an intruder (or a victim) on a *Homo habilis* living site” (Leakey *et al.* 1964: 9). The authors changed their previous interpretation with no substantial new evidence to refute *P. boisei*'s tool-making abilities. Similarly, the discovery of the *P. boisei* mandible KNM-ER 3230 at the FxJj 20 East site (Koobi Fora, Kenya) was not conclusively linked to stone tool-making by Leakey in his 1976 paper (Leakey 1976). This cautious stance again reflects a general reluctance to associate *Paranthropus* with stone tool-making, possibly influenced by the prevailing view that only *Homo* species were capable of such complex behaviours. More recently, at the Nyayanga site in Kenya, the discovery of a *P. boisei* molar in close association with Oldowan artefacts suggests a possible link between *P. boisei* and stone tool use or production. However, Plummer *et al.* (2023) do not definitively attribute the Nyayanga artefacts to a specific hominin genus (i.e., *Paranthropus*), noting rather the presence of early *Homo* remains in Eastern Africa, albeit 1 300 kilometers away “Although not found at Nyayanga, *Homo* was also present in eastern Africa at about the time of Nyayanga deposition (21), so the Nyayanga artifacts cannot be definitively attributed to a specific hominin genus.” This scientifically cautious approach illustrates, in my point of view, the reluctance to attribute tool-making to non-*Homo* hominins. These examples highlight a quite persistent bias in paleoanthropological interpretations, which prefer to consider *Homo* as the primary stone tool-makers despite growing evidence of stone tool use or manufacture by the *Paranthropus* species. This bias reflects the difficulties encountered in overturning long-established views within the scientific community, even in the face of new and convincing evidence.

Homo erectus, is predominantly associated with Acheulean assemblages after 1.4 Ma, but there is evidence at least six occurrences of the association of this taxon with Oldowan stone tools in Ethiopia, Kenya and Tanzania and also Eurasia, as for example at Ubeidiya (e.g., Tobias 1966; Belmaker *et al.* 2002) and Dmanisi (e.g. Lordkipanidze *et al.* 2007, 2013; Mgeladze *et al.* 2011).

The frequent association of *Paranthropus* remains with Oldowan assemblages and the association of certain Oldowan sites with *Homo ergaster/erectus*, as indicated in this article, also highlights the complexity of hominin behaviour and tool-making abilities during the Lower Pleistocene. These observations contest the simplistic view that *Homo* species

were solely responsible for Oldowan artefacts and suggest a more varied and nuanced picture of the cultural behaviour and cognitive development of Lower Pleistocene hominins, challenging previous assumptions and highlighting the multifaceted nature of hominin evolution.

Acknowledgements

I would like to express my gratitude to Jean-Jacques Hublin, for inviting me to present this topic at the Colloquium Lucy's Heirs, in honor of Pr. Yves Coppens. I also extend my thanks to the editors of this special issue of *Comptes Rendus Palevol* “Lucy's heirs-Tribute to Yves Coppens”, Jean-Jacques Hublin, Aurélien Mounier and Nicolas Teyssandier, for the opportunity to contribute to this special issue as well as to the two reviewers for their valuable comments. This text is dedicated to the memory of Professor Yves Coppens, who honoured me by following my various research projects and with whom I was able to work as temporary lecturer at the Collège de France. I would like also to thank Ameline Bardo for her initial comments and Louise Byrne for the english editing. This work is supported by the French Research Agency (Agence nationale de la recherche) ANR HOMTECH (ANR-17-CE27-0005).

REFERENCES

- ALEMSEGED Z., SPOOR F., KIMBEL W. H., BOBE R., GERAADS D., REED D. & WYNN J. G. 2006. — A juvenile early hominin skeleton from Dikika, Ethiopia. *Nature* 443 (7109): 296-301. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nature05047>
- ALEMSEGED Z., BOBE R. & GERAADS D. 2007. — Comparability of fossil data and its significance for the interpretation of hominin environments: a case study in the lower Omo valley, Ethiopia, in BOBE R., ALEMSEGED Z. & BEHRENSMEYER A. K. (eds), *Hominin environments in the East African Pliocene: An assessment of the faunal evidence*. Springer Netherlands Dordrecht: 159-181. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4020-3098-7_7
- ALMÉCJA S. & ALBA D. M. 2014. — On manual proportions and pad-to-pad precision grasping in *Australopithecus afarensis*. *Journal of Human Evolution* 73: 88-92. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhevol.2014.02.006>
- ARCHER W., ALDEIAS V. & MCPHERRON S. P. 2020. — What is ‘in situ’? A reply to Harmand *et al.* (2015). *Journal of Human Evolution* 142: 102740. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhevol.2020.102740>
- ARROYO A., HARMAND S., ROCHE H. & TAYLOR N. 2020. — Searching for hidden activities: percussive tools from the Oldowan and Acheulean of West Turkana, Kenya (2.3–1.76 Ma). *Journal of Archaeological Science* 123: 105238. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jas.2020.105238>
- ASFAW B., BEYENE Y., SEMAW S., SUWA G., WHITE T. & WOLDEGABRIEL G. 1991. — Fejej: a new paleoanthropological research area in Ethiopia. *Journal of Human Evolution* 21 (2): 137-143. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0047-2484\(91\)90004-F](https://doi.org/10.1016/0047-2484(91)90004-F)
- ASFAW B., BEYENE Y., SUWA G., WALTER R. C., WHITE T. D., WOLDEGABRIEL G. & YEMANE T. 1992. — The earliest acheulean from Konso-Gardula. *Nature* 360 (6406): 732-735. <https://doi.org/10.1038/360732a0>
- BAAB K. L., ROGERS M., BRUNER E. & SEMAW S. 2022. — Reconstruction and analysis of the DAN5/P1 and BSN12/P1 Gona Early Pleistocene *Homo* fossils. *Journal of Human Evolution* 162: 103102. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhevol.2021.103102>

- BARDO A., VIGOUROUX L., KIVELL T. L. & POUYDEBAT E. 2018. — The impact of hand proportions on tool grip abilities in humans, great apes and fossil hominins: A biomechanical analysis using musculoskeletal simulation. *Journal of Human Evolution* 125: 106-121. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhevol.2018.10.001>
- BARR W. A. & WOOD B. 2024. — Spatial sampling bias influences our understanding of early hominin evolution in eastern Africa. *Nature Ecology Evolution* 8: 2113-2120. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41559-024-02522-5>
- BARSKY D., CHAPON-SAO C., BAHAIN J. J., BEYENE Y., CAUCHE D., CELIBERTI V., DESCLAUX E., DE LUMLEY H., DE LUMLEY M.-A., MARCHAL F., MOUILLÉ P.-E. & PLEURDEAU D. 2011. — The early Oldowan stone-tool assemblage from Fejej FJ-1a, Ethiopia. *Journal of African Archaeology* 9 (2): 207-224. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/43135551>
- BEDANE T. G., MACKAYE H. T. & BOISSERIE J. R. 2025. — New data on morphological evolution and dietary adaptations of *Elephas recki* from the Plio-Pleistocene Shungura Formation (Lower Omo Valley, Ethiopia). *Peer Community In Paleontology*. <https://doi.org/10.31233/osf.io/qexuf>
- BELMAKER M., TCHERNOV E., CONDEMI S. & BAR-YOSEF O. 2002. — New evidence for hominid presence in the Lower Pleistocene of the Southern Levant. *Journal of Human Evolution* 43 (1): 43-56. <https://doi.org/10.1006/jhev.2002.0556>
- BERILLON G. 1999. — Geometric pattern of the hominoid hallux tarsometatarsal complex. Quantifying the degree of hallux abduction in early hominids. *Comptes Rendus de l'Académie des Sciences-Series IIA-Earth and Planetary Science* 328 (9): 627-633. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S1251-8050\(99\)80160-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1251-8050(99)80160-8)
- BEYENE Y., SUWA G., SANO K., ASFAW B. & KATOH S. 2023. — Konso-Gardula, Ethiopia, in BEYIN A., WRIGHT D. K., WILKINS J. & OLSZEWSKI D. I. (eds), *Handbook of Pleistocene Archaeology of Africa: Hominin behavior, geography, and chronology*. Springer International Publishing, Cham: 421-430. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-20290-2_25
- BIBI F., SOURON A., BOCHERENS H., UNO K. & BOISSERIE J. R. 2013. — Ecological change in the lower Omo Valley around 2.8 Ma. *Biology Letters* 9 (1): 20120890. <https://doi.org/10.1098/rsbl.2012.0890>
- BLUMENSCHINE R. J., PETERS C. R., MASA F. T., CLARKE R. J., DEINO A. L., HAY R. L., SWISHER C. C., STANISTREET I. G., ASHLEY G. M., MCHENRY L. J., SIKES N. E., VAN DER MERWE N. J., TACTIKOS J. C., CUSHING A. E., DEOCAMPO D. M., NJAU J. K. & EBERT J. I. 2003. — Late Pliocene *Homo* and hominid land use from western Olduvai gorge, Tanzania. *Science* 299 (5610): 1217-1221. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.1075374>
- BLUMENSCHINE R. J., STANISTREET I. G., NJAU J. K., BAMFORD M. K., MASAO F. T., ALBERT R. M., STOLLHOFEN H., ANDREWS P., PRASSACK K. A., MCHENRY L. J., FERNÁNDEZ-JALVO Y., CAMILLI E. L. & EBERT J. I. 2012. — Environments and hominin activities across the FLK Peninsula during *Zinjanthropus* times (1.84 Ma), Olduvai Gorge, Tanzania. *Journal of Human Evolution* 63 (2): 364-383. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhevol.2011.10.001>
- BOËS X., VAN BOCXLAER B., PRAT S., FEIBEL C., LEWIS J., ARRIGHI V., TAYLOR N. & HARMAND S. 2024. — Aridity, availability of drinking water and freshwater foods, and hominin and archaeological sites during the Late Pliocene–Early Pleistocene in the western region of the Turkana Basin (Kenya): a review. *Journal of Human Evolution* 186: 103466. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhevol.2023.103466>
- BOISSERIE J. R., GUY F., DELAGNES A., HLUKSO L. J., BIBI F., BEYENE Y. & GUILLEMOT C. 2008. — New palaeoanthropological research in the Plio-Pleistocene Omo group, Lower Omo Valley, SNNPR (southern nations, nationalities and people regions), Ethiopia. *Comptes Rendus Palevol* 7 (7): 429-439. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.crpv.2008.07.010>
- BRAIN C. K., CHURCHER C. S., CLARK J. D., GRINE F. E., SHIPMAN P., SUSMAN R. L., TURNER A. & WATSON V. 1988. — New evidence of early hominids, their culture and environment from the Swartkrans cave, South Africa. *South African Journal of Science* 84: 828-835.
- BRUNER E., HOLLOWAY R., BAAB K. L., ROGERS M. J. & SEMAW S. 2023. — The endocast from Dana Aoule North (DAN5/P1): A 1.5 million year-old human braincase from Gona, Afar, Ethiopia. *American Journal of Biological Anthropology* 181 (2): 206-215. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ajpa.24717>
- CAMPISANO C. J. & FEIBEL C. S. 2008. — Tephrostratigraphy of the Hadar and Busidima Formation at Hadar, Afar Depression, Ethiopia, in QUADE J. & WYNN J. G. (eds), *The Geological Context of Human Evolution in the Horn of Africa*. Vol. 446. Geological Society of America Special Paper, Colorado: 135-162. [https://doi.org/10.1130/2008.2446\(06\)](https://doi.org/10.1130/2008.2446(06))
- CAPARROS M. & PRAT S. 2021. — A phylogenetic networks perspective on reticulate human evolution. *iScience* 24 (4): 102359. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.isci.2021.102359>
- CAZENAVE M., BRAGA J., OETTLÉ A., THACKERAY J. F., DE BEER F., HOFFMAN J., ENDALAMAW M., REDAE B. E. & MACCHIARELLI R. 2017. — Inner structural organization of the distal humerus in *Paranthropus* and *Homo*. *Comptes Rendus Palevol* 16 (5-6): 521-532. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.crpv.2017.06.002>
- CHAPON C., BAHAIN J. J., DE LUMLEY H., PERRENOUD C. & VANDAMME D. 2005. — Stratigraphie, sédimentologie et magnétostratigraphie du site oldowayen de Fejej FJ-1, Sud-Omo, Ethiopie: Premiers résultats. *Quaternaire* 16 (3): 143-152. <https://doi.org/10.4000/quaternaire.360>
- CHAVAILLON J. 1970. — Découverte d'un niveau oldowayen dans la basse vallée de l'Omo (Ethiopie). *Bulletin de la Société préhistorique française* 67 (1): 7-11.
- CHAVAILLON J. 1976. — Evidence for the technical practices of Early Pleistocene hominids, Shungura Formation, Lower Omo Valley, Ethiopia, in COPPENS Y., HOWELL F. C., ISAAC G. L. I. & LEAKEY R. (eds), *Earliest Man and Environments in the Lake Rudolf Basin: Stratigraphy, Paleoecology and Evolution*. University of Chicago Press, Chicago and London: 565-573.
- CHAVAILLON J. & BERTHELET A. 2004. — The archaeological sites of Melka Kunture, in CHAVAILLON J. & PIPERNO M. (eds), *Studies on the Early Paleolithic Site of Melka Kunture, Ethiopia*. IIPP, Florence: 25-80.
- CHAVAILLON J., CHAVAILLON N., COPPENS Y. & SENUT B. 1977. — Présence d'Hominidé dans le site Oldowayen de Gomboré I à Melka-Kunturé. *Comptes Rendus de l'Académie des Sciences Série D* 285: 961-963.
- CLARK J., GONZALO J. & LINARES-MATÁS G. J. 2024. — When to generalise and when to specialise? Climate change and hominin biocultural adaptability in the African early and middle stone age. *Quaternary Science Advances* 15: 100218. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.qsa.2024.100218>
- CLARKE R. J. 2012. — A *Homo habilis* maxilla and other newly-discovered hominid fossils from Olduvai Gorge, Tanzania. *Journal of Human Evolution* 63 (2): 418-428. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhevol.2011.11.007>
- CONDEMI S. 2004. — The garba IV E mandible, in CHAVAILLON J. & PIPERNO M. (eds), *Studies on the Early Paleolithic Site of Melka Kunture, Ethiopia*. IIPP, Florence: 687-701.
- COPPENS Y. 1977. — Hominid remains from the Plio/Pleistocene formations of the Omo Basin, Ethiopia. *Journal of Human Evolution* 6 (2): 169-173. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0047-2484\(77\)80124-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0047-2484(77)80124-3)
- COPPENS Y. 1978. — Evolution of the hominids and of their environment during the Plio-Pleistocene in the lower Omo Valley, Ethiopia. *Geological Society, London, Special Publications* 6 (1): 499-506. <https://doi.org/10.1144/GSL.SP.1978.006.01.34>
- COPPENS Y. 2004. — The hominids of Melka Kunture. Some general reflections, in CHAVAILLON J. & PIPERNO M. (eds), *Studies on the Early Paleolithic site of Melka Kunture, Ethiopia*. IIPP, Florence: 685-686.

- COPPENS Y., CHAVAILLON J. & BEDEN M. 1973. — Résultats de la nouvelle mission de l'Omo (campagne 1972). Découverte de restes d'Hominidés et d'une industrie sur éclats. *Comptes Rendus de l'Académie des Sciences Série D* 276: 161-164.
- DE LUMLEY H. & BEYENE Y. (eds) 2004. — *Les sites préhistoriques de la région de Fejej, Sud-Omo, Éthiopie, dans leur contexte stratigraphique et paléontologique*. Éditions Recherche sur les civilisations, Paris, 635 p.
- DE LUMLEY M.-A. & MARCHAL F. 2004. — Les restes d'hominidés du site de Fejej FJ-1, in DE LUMLEY H. & BEYENE Y. (eds), *Les sites préhistoriques de la région de Fejej, Sud-Omo, Éthiopie, dans leur contexte stratigraphique et paléontologique*. Éditions Recherche sur les Civilisations, Paris: 340-383.
- DE LA TORRE I. 2004. — Omo revisited: evaluating the technological skills of Pliocene hominids. *Current Anthropology* 45 (4): 439-465.
- DE LA TORRE I. 2011. — The origins of stone tool technology in Africa: a historical perspective. *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society B* 366 (1567): 1028-1037. <http://doi.org/10.1098/rstb.2010.0350>
- DE LA TORRE I. & MORA R. 2005 (eds). — *Technological Strategies in the Lower Pleistocene at Olduvai Beds I & II*. ERAUL, Liège, 255 p.
- DE LA TORRE I., BENITO-CALVO A., MARTÍN-RAMOS C., MCHENRY L. J., MORA R., NJAU J. K., PANTE M. C., STANISTREET I. G. & STOLLHOFEN H. 2021. — New excavations in the MNK Skull site, and the last appearance of the Oldowan and *Homo habilis* at Olduvai Gorge, Tanzania. *Journal of Anthropological Archaeology* 61: 101255. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jaa.2020.101255>
- DAY M. H. & NAPIER J. R. 1964. — Hominid fossils from Bed I, Olduvai Gorge, Tanganyika: Fossil foot bones. *Nature* 201: 967-970. <https://doi.org/10.1038/201969a0>
- DEINO A. L. 2012. — ⁴⁰Ar/³⁹Ar dating of Bed I, Olduvai Gorge, Tanzania, and the chronology of early Pleistocene climate change. *Journal of Human Evolution* 63 (2): 251-273. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhevol.2012.05.004>
- DELAGNES A., BOISSERIE J. R., BEYENE Y., CHUNIAUD K., GUILLEMOT C. & SCHUSTER M. 2011. — Archaeological investigations in the Lower Omo Valley (Shungura Formation, Ethiopia): new data and perspectives. *Journal of Human Evolution* 61 (2): 215-222. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhevol.2011.03.008>
- DELAGNES A., GALLAND A., GRAVINA B., BERTRAN P., CORBÉ M., BRENET M., HAILU H. B., SISSAY F. M., ARYA B. G., WOLDET-SADIK M. G. & BOISSERIE J.-R. 2023. — Long-term behavioral adaptation of Oldowan toolmakers to resource-constrained environments at 2.3 Ma in the Lower Omo Valley (Ethiopia). *Scientific Reports* 13: 14350. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-023-40793-3>
- DI VINCENZO F., RODRIGUEZ L., CARRETERO J. M., COLLINA C., GERAADS D., PIPERNO M. & MANZI G. 2015. — The massive fossil humerus from the Oldowan horizon of Gombore I, Melka Kunture (Ethiopia, > 1.39 Ma). *Quaternary Science Review* 122: 207-221. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.quascirev.2015.05.014>
- DIEZ-MARTÍN F., SÁNCHEZ YUSTOS P., URIBELARREA D., BAQUEDANO E., MARK D. F., MABULLA A., FRAILE C., DUQUE J., PÉREZ-GONZÁLEZ A., YRAVEDRA J., EGELAND C. P., ORGANISTA E. & DOMÍNGUEZ-RODRIGO M. 2015. — The origin of the Acheulean: The 1.7 million-year-old site of FLK West, Olduvai Gorge (Tanzania). *Scientific Reports* 5 (1): 17839. <https://doi.org/10.1038/srep17839>
- DOMÍNGUEZ-RODRIGO M. & ALCALÁ L. 2016. — 3.3-million-year-old stone tools and butchery traces? More evidence needed. *PaleoAnthropology* 2016: 46-53. <https://doi.org/10.4207/PA.2016.ART99>
- DOMÍNGUEZ-RODRIGO M. & ALCALÁ L. 2019. — Pliocene archaeology at Lomekwi 3? New evidence fuels more skepticism. *Journal of African Archaeology* 17 (2): 173-176. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/26869050>
- DOMÍNGUEZ-RODRIGO M., MABULLA A., BUNN H. T., BARBA R., DIEZ-MARTÍN F., EGELAND C. P., ESPÍLEZ E., EGELAND A., YRAVEDRA J. & SÁNCHEZ P. 2009. — Unraveling hominin behavior at another anthropogenic site from Olduvai Gorge (Tanzania): new archaeological and taphonomic research at BK, Upper Bed II. *Journal of Human Evolution* 57 (3): 260-283. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhevol.2009.04.006>
- DOMÍNGUEZ-RODRIGO M., PICKERING T. R. & BUNN H. T. 2011. — Reply to McPherron *et al.*: Doubting Dikika is about data, not paradigms. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences* 108 (21): E117. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1104647108>
- DOMÍNGUEZ-RODRIGO M., PICKERING T. R., BAQUEDANO E., MABULLA A., MARK D. F., MUSIBA C., BUNN H. T., URIBELARREA D., SMITH V., DIEZ-MARTÍN F., PÉREZ-GONZÁLEZ A., SÁNCHEZ P., SANTONJA M., BARBONI D., GIDNA A., ASHLEY G., YRAVEDRA J., HEATON J. L. & ARRIAZA M. C. 2013. — First partial skeleton of a 1.34-million-year-old *Paranthropus boisei* from Bed II, Olduvai Gorge, Tanzania. *PLoS ONE* 8 (12): e80347. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0080347>
- DOMÍNGUEZ-RODRIGO M., PICKERING T. R., ALMÉCIJA S., HEATON J. L., BAQUEDANO E., MABULLA A. & URIBELARREA D. 2015. — Earliest modern human-like hand bone from a new >1.84-million-year-old site at Olduvai in Tanzania. *Nature Communication* 6 (1): 7987. <https://doi.org/10.1038/ncomms8987>
- DUNMORE C. J., SKINNER M. M., BARDO A., BERGER L. R., HUBLIN J.-J., PAHR D. H., ROSAS A., STEPHENS N. B. & KIVELL T. L. 2020. — The position of *Australopithecus sediba* within fossil hominin hand use diversity. *Nature Ecology and Evolution* 4 (7): 911-918. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41559-020-1207-5>
- FEIBEL C. S., BROWN F. H. & MCDUGALL I. 1989. — Stratigraphic context of fossil hominids from the Omo Group deposits: Northern Turkana Basin, Kenya and Ethiopia. *American Journal of Physical Anthropology* 78 (4): 595-622. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ajpa.1330780412>
- FOLEY R. 2002. — Adaptive radiations and dispersals in hominin evolutionary ecology. *Evolutionary Anthropology* 11 (S1): 32-37. <https://doi.org/10.1002/evan.10051>
- GALLOTTI R. & MUSSI M. 2015. — The unknown Oldowan: ~1.7-million-year-old standardized obsidian small tools from Garba IV, Melka Kunture, Ethiopia. *PLoS ONE* 10 (12): e0145101. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0145101>
- GÉRARD C., BARDO A., GUÉRY J. P., POUYDEBAT E., SIMMEN B. & NARAT V. 2022. — Manipulative repertoire of bonobos (*Pan paniscus*) in spontaneous feeding situation. *American Journal of Primatology* 84 (7): e23383. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ajp.23383>
- GOLDMAN-NEUMAN T. & HOVERS E. 2012. — Raw material selectivity in Late Pliocene Oldowan sites in the Makaamitalu Basin, Hadar, Ethiopia. *Journal of Human Evolution* 62 (3): 353-366. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhevol.2011.05.006>
- GREEN D. J. & GORDON A. D. 2008. — Metacarpal proportions in *Australopithecus africanus*. *Journal of Human Evolution* 54 (5): 705-719. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhevol.2007.10.007>
- GRINE F. E., MONGLE C. S., FLEAGLE J. G. & HAMMOND A. S. 2022. — The taxonomic attribution of African hominin postcrania from the Miocene through the Pleistocene: Associations and assumptions. *Journal of Human Evolution* 173: 103255. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhevol.2022.103255>
- HARMAND S. 2009. — Raw material selectivity and techno-economic behaviours at Oldowan Acheulean sites in the West Turkana region, Kenya, in ADAMS B. & BLADES B. (eds), *Lithic Materials and Paleolithic Societies*. Blackwell Publishing, Oxford: 3-14.
- HARMAND S., LEWIS J. E., FEIBEL C. S., LEPRE C. J., PRAT S., LENOBLE A., BOËS X., QUINN R. L., BRENET M., ARROYO A., TAYLOR N., CLÉMENT S., DAVER G., BRUGAL J.-P., LEAKEY L., MORTLOCK R. A., WRIGHT J. D., LOKORODI S., KIRWA C., KENT D. V. & ROCHE H. 2015. — 3.3-million-year-old stone tools from Lomekwi 3, West Turkana, Kenya. *Nature* 521 (7552): 310-315. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nature14464>

- HARMAND S., LEWIS J. E., TAYLOR N., FEIBEL C. S., BOËS X., PRAT S. & ROCHE H. 2019. — Reply to Domínguez-Rodrigo and Alcalá: interpretation without accurate evidence is fantasy. *Journal of African archaeology* 17 (2): 177-181.
- HARRIS J. W. & HERBICH I. 1978. — Aspects of early Pleistocene hominid behaviour east of Lake Turkana, Kenya. *Geological Society, London, Special Publications* 6 (1): 529-547.
- HATALA K. G., ROACH N. T., BEHRENSMEYER A. K., FALKINGHAM P. L., GATESY S. M., WILLIAMS-HATALA E. M., FEIBEL C. S., DALACHA I., KIRINYA M., LINGA E., LOKI R., ALKORO A., LONGAYE M., LONYERICH O., LOYAPAN I., NAKUDO N., NYETE C. & LEAKEY L. N. 2024. — Footprint evidence for locomotor diversity and shared habitats among early Pleistocene hominins. *Science* 386 (6725): 1004-1010. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.ado5275>
- HUSKO L. J., GUY F., MODESTO-MATA M., MARTINEZ DE PINILLOS M., BRASIL M. F., TOWLE I., THIEBAUT A. & BOISSERIE J.-R. 2024. — Taxonomic assignments for the 3.4 Ma to 1.1 Ma hominin postcranial teeth from the Usno Formation and the Shungura Formation, Lower Omo Valley, Ethiopia. *PaleorXiv Papers*. <https://doi.org/10.31233/osf.io/g7kfx>
- KEY A. & PROFFITT T. 2024. — Revising the oldest Oldowan: Updated optimal linear estimation models and the impact of Nyayanga (Kenya). *Journal of Human Evolution* 186: 103468.
- KEY A. J., DUNMORE C. J. & MARZKE M. W. 2019. — The unexpected importance of the fifth digit during stone tool production. *Scientific Reports* 9 (16724): 1-8. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-019-53332-w>
- KIMBEL W. H. & DELEZENE L. K. 2009. — “Lucy” redux: a review of research on *Australopithecus afarensis*. *American journal of physical anthropology* 140 (S49): 2-48. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ajpa.21183>
- KIMBEL W. H., JOHANSON D. C. & RAK Y. 1997. — Systematic assessment of a maxilla of *Homo* from Hadar, Ethiopia. *American Journal of Physical Anthropology* 103 (2): 235-262. [https://doi.org/10.1002/\(SICI\)1096-8644\(199706\)103:2%3C235::AID-AJPA8%3E3.0.CO;2-S](https://doi.org/10.1002/(SICI)1096-8644(199706)103:2%3C235::AID-AJPA8%3E3.0.CO;2-S)
- KIMBEL W. H., WALTER R. C., JOHANSON D. C., REED K. E., ARONSON J. L., ASSEFA Z., MAREAN C. W., ECK G. G., BOBE R., HOVERS E., RAK Y., VONDRA C., YEMANE T., YORK D., CHEN Y., EVENSEN N. M. & SMITH P. E. 1996. — Late Pliocene *Homo* and Oldowan Tools from the Hadar Formation (Kada Hadar Member), Ethiopia. *Journal of Human Evolution* 31 (6): 549-561. <https://doi.org/10.1006/jhev.1996.0079>
- KIVELL T. L. 2015. — Evidence in hand: recent discoveries and the early evolution of human manual manipulation. *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society B: Biological Sciences* 370 (1682): 20150105. <https://doi.org/10.1098/rstb.2015.0105>
- KIVELL T. L., BARAKI N., LOCKWOOD V., WILLIAMS-HATALA E. M. & WOOD B. A. 2022. — Form, function and evolution of the human hand. *Yearbook of Biological Anthropology Article* 181 (S76): 6-57. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ajpa.24667>
- KIVELL T. L., KIBII J. M., CHURCHILL S. E., SCHMID P. & BERGER L. R. 2011. — *Australopithecus sediba* hand demonstrates mosaic evolution of locomotor and manipulative abilities. *Science* 333 (6048): 1411-1417. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.1202625>
- KIVELL T. L., OSTROFSKY K. R., RICHMOND B. G. & DRAPEAU M. S. M. 2020. — Metacarpals and manual phalanges, in ZIPPEL B., RICHMOND B. G. & WARD C. V. (eds), *Hominin postcranial remains from Sterkfontein, South Africa, 1936-1995*. Oxford University Press, Oxford: 106-143. <https://doi.org/10.1093/oso/9780197507667.003.0009>
- KUNZE J., HARVATI K., HOTZ G. & KARAKOSTIS F. A. 2024. — Humanlike manual activities in *Australopithecus*. *Journal of human evolution* 196: 103591. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhevol.2024.103591>
- LAGUE M. R. & JUNGERS W. L. 1996. — Morphometric variation in Plio-Pleistocene hominid distal humeri. *American Journal of Physical Anthropology* 101 (3): 401-427. [https://doi.org/10.1002/\(SICI\)1096-8644\(199611\)101:3%3C401::AID-AJPA8%3E3.0.CO;2-0](https://doi.org/10.1002/(SICI)1096-8644(199611)101:3%3C401::AID-AJPA8%3E3.0.CO;2-0)
- LEAKEY L. S. B. 1959. — A new fossil skull from Olduvai. *Nature* 184: 491-493. <https://doi.org/10.1038/184491a0>
- LEAKEY L. S. B., TOBIAS P. V. & NAPIER J. R. 1964. — A new species of the genus *Homo* from Olduvai Gorge. *Nature* 202: 7-9. <https://doi.org/10.1038/202007a0>
- LEAKEY M. D. 1971. — *Olduvai Gorge. Vol 3. Excavations in Beds I and II, 1960-1963*. Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, 306 p.
- LEAKEY R. E. F. 1976. — New hominid fossils from the Koobi Fora formation in northern Kenya. *Nature* 261: 574-576. <https://doi.org/10.1038/261574a0>
- LEAKEY M. D., CLARKE R. J. & LEAKEY L. S. B. 1971. — New Hominid skull from Bed I, Olduvai Gorge, Tanzania. *Nature* 232: 308-312. <https://doi.org/10.1038/232308a0>
- LEAKEY M. G., SPOOR F., BROWN F. H., GATHOGO P. N., KIARIE C., LEAKEY L. N. & MCDUGALL I. 2001. — New hominin genus from eastern Africa shows diverse middle Pliocene lineages. *Nature* 410: 433-440. <https://doi.org/10.1038/35068500>
- LEAKEY R. E. F. 1974. — Further evidence of lower Pleistocene hominids from east Rudolf, North Kenya, 1973. *Nature* 248 (5450): 653-656. <https://doi.org/10.1038/248653a0>
- LEPRE C. J., ROCHE H., KENT D. V., HARMAND S., QUINN R. L., BRUGAL J. P., TEXIER P. J., LENOBLE A. & FEIBEL C. S. 2011. — An earlier origin for the Acheulian. *Nature* 477 (7362): 82-85. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nature10372>
- LORDKIPANIDZE D., JASHASHVILI T., VEKUA A., DE LEÓN M. S. P., ZOLLIKOFER C. P. E., RIGHTMIRE G. P., PONTZER H., FERRING R., OMS O., TAPPEN M., BUKHSHANIDZE M., AGUSTI J., KAHLKE R., KILADZE G., MARTINEZ-NAVARRO B., MOUSKHELISHVILI A., NIORADZE M. & ROOK L. 2007. — Postcranial evidence from early *Homo* from Dmanisi, Georgia. *Nature* 449: 305-310. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nature06134>
- LORDKIPANIDZE D., DE LEÓN M. S. P., MARGVELASHVILI A., RAK Y., RIGHTMIRE G. P., VEKUA A. & ZOLLIKOFER C. P. E. 2013. — A Complete Skull from Dmanisi, Georgia, and the Evolutionary Biology of early *Homo*. *Science* 342 (6156): 326-331. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.1238484>
- LORENTE-GALDOS B., LAO O., SERRA-VIDAL G., SANTPERE G., KUDERNA L. F., ARAUNA L. R., FADHLOU-ZID K., PIMENOFF V., SOODYALL H., ZALLOUA P., MARQUES-BONET T. & COMAS D. 2019. — Whole-genome sequence analysis of a Pan African set of samples reveals archaic gene flow from an extinct basal population of modern humans into sub-Saharan populations. *Genome biology* 20 (77): 1-15. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13059-019-1684-5>
- MACCHI R., DAVER G., BRENET M., PRAT S., HUGHEVILLE L., HARMAND S., LEWIS J. & DOMALAIN M. 2021. — Biomechanical demands of percussive techniques in the context of early stone toolmaking. *Journal of the Royal Society Interface* 18 (178): 20201044. <https://doi.org/10.1098/rsif.2020.1044>
- MANA S., HEMMING S., KENT D. V. & LEPRE C. J. 2019. — Temporal and stratigraphic framework for paleoanthropology sites within East-Central Area 130, Koobi Fora, Kenya. *Frontiers in Earth Science* 7: 230. <https://doi.org/10.3389/feart.2019.00230>
- MANAFZADEH A. R. & GATESY S. M. 2021. — Paleobiological reconstructions of articular function require all six degrees of freedom. *Journal of Anatomy* 239 (6): 1516-1524. <https://doi.org/10.1111/joa.13513>
- MARZKE M. W. 1983. — Joint functions and grips of the *Australopithecus afarensis* hand, with special reference to the region of the capitate. *Journal of Human Evolution* 12 (2): 197-211. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0047-2484\(83\)80025-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0047-2484(83)80025-6)

- MARZKE M. W. 1997. — Precision grips, hand morphology, and tools. *American Journal of Physical Anthropology* 102 (1): 91-110. [https://doi.org/10.1002/\(SICI\)1096-8644\(199701\)102:1%3C91::AID-AJPA8%3E3.0.CO;2-G](https://doi.org/10.1002/(SICI)1096-8644(199701)102:1%3C91::AID-AJPA8%3E3.0.CO;2-G)
- MARZKE M. W. 2013. — Tool making, hand morphology and fossil hominins. *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society B: Biological Sciences* 368 (1630): 20120414. <https://doi.org/doi:10.1098/rstb.2012.0414>
- MARZKE M. W., MARCHANT L. F., MCGREW W. C. & REECE S. P. 2015. — Grips and hand movements of chimpanzees during feeding in Mahale Mountains National Park, Tanzania. *American Journal of Physical Anthropology* 156 (3): 317-326. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ajpa.22651>
- MCDUGALL I. A. N. & BROWN F. H. 2008. — Geochronology of the pre-KBS tuff sequence, Omo Group, Turkana Basin. *Journal of the Geological Society London* 165 (2): 549-562. <https://doi.org/10.1144/0016-76492006-170>
- MCHEMRY L. J. 2012. — A revised stratigraphic framework for Olduvai Gorge Bed I based on tuff geochemistry. *Journal of Human Evolution* 63 (2): 284-299. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhevol.2011.04.010>
- MCPHERRON S. P., ALEMSEGED Z., MAREAN C. W., WYNN J. G., REED D., GERAADS D., BOBE R. & BÉARAT H. A. 2010. — Evidence for stone-tool-assisted consumption of animal tissues before 3.39 million years ago at Dikika, Ethiopia. *Nature* 466: 857-860. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nature09248>
- MERCADER J., AKUKU P., BOIVIN N., BUGUMBA R., BUSHOZI P., CAMACHO A., CARTER T., CLARKE S., CUEVA-TEMPRANA A., DURKIN P., FAVREAU J., FELLA K., HABERLE S., HUBBARD S., INWOOD J., ITAMBU M., KOROMO S., LEE P., MOHAMMED A., MWANBWIGA A., OLESILAU L., PATALANO R., ROBERTS P., RULE S., SALADIE P., SILJEDAL G., SOTO M., UMBSAAR J. & PETRAGLIA M. 2021. — Earliest Olduvai hominins exploited unstable environments ~2 million years ago. *Nature Communications* 12 (1): 3. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-020-20176-2>
- MGELADZE A., LORDKIPANIDZE D., MONCEL M.-H., DESPRIÉE J., CHAGELISHVILI R., NIORADZE M. & NIORADZE G. 2011. — Hominin occupations at the Dmanisi site, Georgia, Southern Caucasus: Raw materials and technical behaviours of Europe's first hominins. *Journal of Human Evolution* 60: 571-596. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhevol.2010.10.008>
- MORGAN L. E., RENNE P. R., KIEFFER G., PIPERNO M., GALLOTTI R. & RAYNAL J. P. 2012. — A chronological framework for a long and persistent archaeological record: Melka Kunture, Ethiopia. *Journal of Human Evolution* 62 (1): 104-115. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhevol.2011.10.007>
- MOYÀ-SOLÀ S., KOHLER M., ALBA D. M. & ALMÉCIJA S. 2008. — Taxonomic attribution of the Olduvai hominid 7 manual remains and the functional interpretation of hand morphology in robust australopithecines. *Folia Primatologica* 79 (4): 215-50. <https://doi.org/10.1159/000113458>
- MUSSI M., SKINNER M. M., MELIS R. T., PANERA J., RUBIO-JARA S., DAVIES T. W., GERAADS D., BOCHERENS H., BRIATICO G., LE CABEC A., HUBLIN J.-J., GIDNA A., BONNEFILLE R., DI BIANCO L. & MÉNDEZ-QUINTAS E. 2023. — Early *Homo erectus* lived at high altitudes and produced both Oldowan and Acheulean tools. *Science* 382 (6671): 713-718. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.add9115>
- NAPIER J. R. 1956. — The prehensile movements of the human hand. *Journal of Bone and Joint Surgery* 38-B(4): 902-13. <https://doi.org/10.1302/0301-620X.38B4.902>
- NAPIER J. R. 1962. — Fossil hand bones from Olduvai Gorge. *Nature* 196: 409-411. <https://doi.org/10.1038/196409a0>
- NEUFUSS J., ROBBINS M., BAEUMER J., HULME T. & KIVELL T. 2018. — Manual skills for food processing by mountain gorillas in Bwindi Impenetrable National Park, Uganda. *Biological Journal of the Linnean Society* 127 (3): 543-562.
- PLUMMER T. 2004. — Flaked stones and old bones: biological and cultural evolution at the dawn of technology. *American Journal of Physical Anthropology* 2004 (S39): 118-164. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ajpa.20157>
- PLUMMER T., OLIVER J. S., FINESTONE E. M., DITCHFIELD P. W., BISHOP L. C., BLUMENTHAL S. A., LEMORINI C., CARICOLA I., BAILEY S., HERRIES A. L. R., PARKINSON J. A., WHITFIELD E., HERTEL F., KINYANJUI R. N., VINCENT T., LI. Y., LOUYS J., FROST S. R., BRAUN D. R., REEVES J. S., EARLY E. D. G., ONYANGO B., LAMELA-LOPEZ R., FORREST F. L., HE H., LANE T. P., FROUIN M., NOMADE S., WILSON E. P., BARTILOL S., ROTICH N. K. & POTTS R. 2023. — Expanded geographic distribution and dietary strategies of the earliest Oldowan hominins and *Paranthropus*. *Science* 379 (6632): 561-566. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.abo7452>
- POTTS R. 2012. — Evolution and environmental change in early human prehistory. *Annual Review of Anthropology* 41: 151-167. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-anthro-092611-145754>
- PRAT S. 2002. — Anatomical study of the skull of the Kenyan specimen KNM-ER 1805: a re-evaluation of its taxonomic allocation? *Comptes Rendus Palevol* 1 (1): 27-33. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S1631-0683\(02\)00001-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1631-0683(02)00001-5)
- PRAT S. 2022. — Emergence of the genus *Homo*: From concept to taxonomy. *L'Anthropologie* 126 (4): 103068. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.anthro.2022.103068>
- PRAT S. 2023. — Beyond the genus stereotype. Who were the first toolmakers in Africa? Crossed views between archaeology and anatomy. *L'Anthropologie* 127 (4): 103187. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.anthro.2023.103187>
- PRAT S., BRUGAL J.-P., ROCHE H. & TEXIER P.-J. 2003. — Nouvelles découvertes de dents d'hominidés dans le membre Kaitio de la formation de Nachukui (1,65-1,9 Ma), Ouest du lac Turkana (Kenya). *Comptes Rendus Palevol* 2 (8): 685-693. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.crpv.2003.07.001>
- PRAT S., BRUGAL J. P., TIERCELIN J. J., BARRAT J. A., BOHN M., DELAGNES A., HARMAND S., KIMEU K., KIBUNJIA M., TEXIER P.-J. & ROCHE H. 2005. — First occurrence of early *Homo* in the Nachukui formation (West Turkana, Kenya) at 2.3-2.4 Myr. *Journal of Human Evolution* 49 (2): 230-240. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhevol.2005.03.009>
- REED D. N., RANEY E., JOHNSON J., JACKSON H., VIRABALIN N. & MBONU N. 2023. — Hominin nomenclature and the importance of information systems for managing complexity in paleo-anthropology. *Journal of Human Evolution* 175: 103308. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhevol.2022.103308>
- RICHMOND B. G., GREEN D. J., LAGUE M. R., CHIRCHIR H., BEHRENSMEYER A. K., BOBE R., BAMFORD M. K., GRIFFIN N. L., GUNZ P., MBUA E., MERRITT S. R., POBINER B., KIURA P., KIBUNJIA M., HARRIS J. W. K. & BRAUN D. R. 2020. — The upper limb of *Paranthropus boisei* from Ileret, Kenya. *Journal of Human Evolution* 141: 102727. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhevol.2019.102727>
- RICHMOND B. G., ROACH N. T. & OSTROFSKY K. R. 2016. — Evolution of the early hominin hand, in KIVELL T., LEMELIN P., RICHMOND B. & SCHMITT D. (eds), *The Evolution of the Primate Hand. Developments in Primatology: Progress and Prospects*. Springer, New York, NY: 515-543. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4939-3646-5_18
- ROACH N. T. & LIEBERMAN D. E. 2014. — Upper body contributions to power generation during rapid, overhand throwing in humans. *The Journal of Experimental Biology* 217: 2139-2149. <https://doi.org/10.1242/jeb.103275>
- ROACH N. T., VENKADESAN M., RAINBOW M. J. & LIEBERMAN D. E. 2013. — Elastic energy storage in the shoulder and the evolution of high-speed throwing in *Homo*. *Nature* 498: 483-486. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nature12267>
- ROCHE H., BRUGAL J.-P., DELAGNES A., FEIBEL C., HARMAND S., KIBUNJIA M., PRAT S. & TEXIER P.-J. 2003. — Les sites archéo-

- logiques plio-pléistocènes de la formation de Nachukui, Ouest-Turkana, Kenya: bilan synthétique 1997-2001. *Comptes Rendus Palevol* 2 (8): 663-673. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.crpv.2003.06.001>
- ROCHE H., BLUMENSCHINE R. J. & SHEA J. J. 2009. — Origins and adaptations of early genus *Homo*: what archeology tells us, in GRINE F. E., FLEAGLE J. G. & LEAKEY R. E. (eds), *The First Humans: Origin and Early Evolution of the Genus Homo*. Springer, Dordrecht: 135-147. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4020-9980-9_12
- ROLIAN C., LIEBERMAN D. E. & ZERMENO J. P. 2011. — Hand biomechanics during simulated stone tool use. *Journal of Human Evolution* 61 (1): 26-41. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhevol.2011.01.008>
- ROWAN J., LAZAGABASTER I. A., CAMPISANO C. J., BIBI F., BOBE R., BOISSERIE J. R., FROST S. R., GETACHEW T., GILBERT C. C., LEWIS M. E., MELAKU S., SCOTT E., SOURON A., WERDELIN L., KIMBEL W. H. & REED K. E. 2022. — Early Pleistocene large mammals from Maka'amitalu, Hadar, lower Awash valley, Ethiopia. *PeerJ* 10: e13210. <https://doi.org/10.7717/peerj.13210>
- SEMAW S., ROGERS M. J., SIMPSON S. W., LEVIN N. E., QUADE J., DUNBAR N., MCINTOSH W. C., CÁCERES I., STINCHCOMB G. E., HOLLOWAY R. L., BROWN F. H., BUTLER R. F., STOUT D. & EVERETT M. 2020. — Co-occurrence of Acheulian and Oldowan artifacts with *Homo erectus* cranial fossils from Gona, Afar, Ethiopia. *Science Advances* 6 (10): eaaw4694. <https://doi.org/10.1126/sciadv.aaw4694>
- SENUB B. 1979. — Comparaison des Hominidés de Gomboré IB et de Kanapoi; deux pièces du genre *Homo*? *Bulletins et Mémoires de la Société d'Anthropologie de Paris* XIII Série 6: 111-117.
- SKINNER M. M., STEPHENS N. B., TSEGAI Z. J., FOOTE A. C., NGUYEN N. H., GROSS T., PAHR D. H., HUBLIN J.-J. & KIVELL T. L. 2015. — Human-like hand use in *Australopithecus africanus*. *Science* 347 (6220): 395-399. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.1261735>
- SPOOR F., GUNZ P., NEUBAUER S., STELZER S., SCOTT N., KWEKASON A. & DEAN. C. 2015. — Reconstructed *Homo habilis* type OH 7 suggests deep-rooted species diversity in early *Homo*. *Nature* 519: 83-86. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nature14224>
- SUSMAN R. L. 1991. — Who made the Oldowan tools? Fossil evidence for tool behavior in Plio-Pleistocene hominids. *Journal of Anthropological Research* 47 (2): 129-151. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/3630322>
- SUSMAN R. L. & CREEL N. 1979. — Functional and morphological affinities of the subadult hand (OH 7) from Olduvai Gorge. *American Journal of Physical Anthropology* 51 (3): 311-331. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ajpa.1330510303>
- SUWA G. 1990. — *A comparative analysis of hominid dental remains from the Shungura and Usno Formations, Omo Valley, Ethiopia*. PhD thesis. University of California, Berkeley, 522 p.
- SUWA G., WHITE T. D. & HOWELL F. C. 1996. — Mandibular postcanine dentition from the Shungura Formation, Ethiopia: Crown morphology, taxonomic allocation, and plio-pleistocene hominid evolution. *American Journal of Physical Anthropology* 101 (2): 247-282. [https://doi.org/10.1002/\(SICI\)1096-8644\(199610\)101:2%3C247::AID-AJPA9%3E3.0.CO;2-Z](https://doi.org/10.1002/(SICI)1096-8644(199610)101:2%3C247::AID-AJPA9%3E3.0.CO;2-Z)
- TAMRAT E., THOUVENY N., TAIEB M. & BRUGAL J. P. 2014. — Magnetostratigraphic study of the Melka Kunture archaeological site (Ethiopia) and its chronological implications. *Quaternary International* 343: 5-16. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.quaint.2013.11.030>
- THOMPSON J. C., MCPHERSON S. P., BOBE R., REED D., BARR W. A., WYNN J. G., MAREAN C.W., GERAADS D. & ALEMSEGED Z. 2015. — Taphonomy of fossils from the hominin-bearing deposits at Dikika, Ethiopia. *Journal of human evolution* 86: 112-135. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhevol.2015.06.013>
- TOBIAS P. V. 1966. — Fossil hominid remains from Ubeidiya, Israel. *Nature* 211 (5045): 130-133. <https://doi.org/10.1038/211130a0>
- TOBIAS P. V. 1991. — *Olduvai gorge Vol 4a et 4b. Homo habilis: skulls, endocasts and teeth*. Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, 894 p.
- TOCHERI M. W., MARZKE M. W., LIU D., BAE M., JONES G. P., WILLIAMS R. C. & RAZDAN A. 2003. — Functional capabilities of modern and fossil hominid hands: Three-dimensional analysis of trapezia. *American Journal of Physical Anthropology* 122 (2): 101-112. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ajpa.10235>
- VILLMOARE B., KIMBEL W. H., SEYOUM C., CAMPISANO C. J., DIMAGGIO E. N., ROWAN J., BRAUN D. R., ARROWSMITH J. R. & REED K. E. 2015. — Early *Homo* at 2.8 Ma from Ledi-Geraru, Afar, Ethiopia. *Science* 347 (6228): 1352-1354. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.aaa1343>
- VILLMOARE B., DELEZENE L. K., RECTOR A. L., DIMAGGIO E. N., CAMPISANO C. J., FEARY D. A., ALI B. M., CHUPIK D., DEINO A. L., GARELLO D. I., HAYIDARA M. A., LOCKE E. M., OMAR O. A., ROBINSON J. R., SCOTT E., SMAI I. E., GELETA TEREFE K., WERDELIN L., KIMBEL W. H., ARROWSMITH J. R. & REED K. E. 2025. — New discoveries of *Australopithecus* and *Homo* from Ledi-Geraru, Ethiopia. *Nature*. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-025-09390-4>
- WARD C. V., TOCHERI M. W., PLAVCAN J. M., BROWN F. H. & MANTHI F. K. 2014. — Early Pleistocene third metacarpal from Kenya and the evolution of modern human-like hand morphology. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America* 111 (1): 121-124. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1316014111>
- WHITE T. D. 1988. — The comparative biology of “robust” *Australopithecus*: clues from context, in GRINE F. E. (ed.), *Evolutionary history of the “Robust” australopithecines*. Aldine de Gruyter, New York: 449-483.
- WHITE T. 2003. — Early hominids—diversity or distortion? *Science* 299 (5615): 1994-1997. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.1078294>
- WILLIAMS E. M., GORDON A. D. & RICHMOND B. G. 2010. — Upper limb kinematics and the role of the wrist during stone tool production. *American Journal of Physical Anthropology* 143 (1): 134-145. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ajpa.21302>
- WILLIAMS E. M., GORDON A. D. & RICHMOND B. G. 2012. — Hand pressure distribution during Oldowan stone tool production. *Journal of Human Evolution* 62 (4): 520-532. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhevol.2012.02.005>
- WILLIAMS E. M., GORDON A. D. & RICHMOND B. G. 2014. — Biomechanical strategies for accuracy and force generation during stone tool production. *Journal of Human Evolution* 72: 52-63. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhevol.2014.03.004>
- WILLIAMS-HATALA E. M., HATALA K. G., GORDON M., KEY A., KASPER M. & KIVELL T. L. 2018. — The manual pressures of stone tool behaviors and their implications for the evolution of the human hand. *Journal of Human Evolution* 119: 14-26. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhevol.2018.02.008>
- WILLIAMS-HATALA E. M., HATALA K. G., KEY A., DUNMORE C. J., KASPER M., GORDON M. & KIVELL T. L. 2021. — Kinetics of stone tool production among novice and expert tool makers. *American Journal of Physical Anthropology* 174 (4): 714-727. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ajpa.24159>
- WOOD B. A. 1991. — *Koobi Fora Project Vol 4: Hominid Remains From Koobi Fora*. Clarendon Press, Oxford, 466 p.
- WOOD B. A. 1997. — The oldest whodunnit in the world. *Nature* 385: 292-293. <https://doi.org/10.1038/385292a0>
- WOOD B. A. & BOYLE E. K. 2016. — Hominin taxic diversity: Fact or fantasy? *American journal of physical Anthropology* 159 (S61): S37-S78. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ajpa.22902>
- WOOD B. A. & CONSTANTINO P. 2007. — *Paranthropus boisei*: fifty years of evidence and analysis. *American Journal of Physical Anthropology* 134 (S45): 106-132. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ajpa.20732>
- WOOD B. & LEAKEY M. 2011. — The Omo-Turkana Basin fossil hominins and their contribution to our understanding of human evolution in Africa. *Evolutionary Anthropology* 20 (6): 264-292. <https://doi.org/10.1002/evan.20335>

WOOD B. A. & LONERGAN N. 2008. — The hominin fossil record: taxa, grades and clades. *Journal of anatomy* 212 (4): 354-376. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1469-7580.2008.00871.x>

ZANOLLI C., DEAN M. C., ASSEFA Y., BAYLE P., BRAGA J., CONDEMI S., ENDALAMAW M., ENGDA REDAE B. & MACCHIARELLI R. 2016. —

Structural organization and tooth development in a *Homo* aff. *erectus* juvenile mandible from the Early Pleistocene site of Garba IV at Melka Kunture, Ethiopian highlands. *American Journal of Physical Anthropology* 162 (3): 533-549. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ajpa.23135>

*Submitted on 15 February 2024;
accepted on 3 July 2025;
published on 5 December 2025.*